

PDSA experiences at WVU
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In the spring semester of 2022, we asked all professors who engaged in PDSA work at WVU over the last four years to submit the names of any student who participated and the activity type they implemented. Not all faculty who conducted a PDSA responded, but from the ones who did we collected 1331 unique student names. We then requested information from Institutional Research about their entering major and their current major. We also requested their gender and first generation status. Of the 1331 students, there were 423 who entered the university as STEM majors. These were the focus of our study.

The PDSA activities included:

- Immersion Applicant Interviews- Spring 2021
- Pre-Immersion, Connect Mentors and Participants- Summer 2021
- Immersion Mentor Interviews- Spring 2021
- Embedded Students- Fall 2020
- Embedded Students- Spring 2021
- Meet and Greet (Mid-Semester Zoom Check In)- Fall 2020
- SURE Virtual Coursework- Summer 2020
- Student Research Presentation- Summer 2020
- Student Research Presentation- Spring 2020
- Connecting to Campus Resources- Spring 2020
- Ambassadors for Change Course v2- Spring 2020
- Eliminating Exams and Using Frequent Quizzes- Fall 2020 ASTR106
- Empowering Students Mental Health- Fall 2020 ASTR106
- Empowering Students Mental Health- Spring 2021 ASTR106
- Just for Fun Welcome Video- Spring 2021 ASTR106
- Teaching Students "How to Learn"- Spring 2020
- Math Anxiety Support- Spring 2020 Math 106
- Math Anxiety Support- Spring 2022 Math 104
- Math Anxiety Support- Fall 2021 Math 106

We tried to answer the question: “Does engaging in First2 activities result in higher persistence in STEM?” Out of the 423 STEM majors that participated in at least one First2 PDSA activity, 198 (46.8%) remained in a STEM degree and 225 (53.2%) left STEM.

Of the 225 students that left the STEM pathway

- 91 (21.5%) of them ended up dropping out of college
- 104 (24.6%) switched their major to a non-STEM degree (this includes 17 (4%) who switched to Psychology)
- 16 (3.8%) of the students who left switched to a Health related major (7 to Exercise Physiology, 2 to Health and Well-Being, 2 to a Healthcare Pathway, 2 to Public Health, 2 to Sport and Exercise Psychology, and 1 to Pre-Nursing)

- 14 (3.3%) of the students switched to a STEM adjacent major (4 to Animal & Nutritional Sciences, 5 to Environmental, Soil & Water Science, 2 to Environmental Microbiology, 2 to Wildlife & Fisheries Resources, and 1 to Environmental Geoscience)

Students participating in at least one First2 activity had a higher persistence rate in STEM (46.8%) than the current WVU STEM persistence rate (27%).

Different Types of Experiences

We tried to answer the question: “Do some First2 activities produce better persistence results?” We had data for 14 students who participated in a summer immersion program. Of these eight (57.1%) persisted in STEM, while six (42.9%) left STEM. Of those six who left STEM, four left the university and the remaining two switched to non-STEM degrees, one being Psychology.

Of the 268 students who participated in a semester-long PDSA activity, 125 (46.6%) persisted in STEM while 143 (53.4%) left. Of those 143, 77 left the university and 66 switched to non-STEM degrees. Two students who persisted in STEM have graduated with Chemistry and Chemical Engineering degrees. It is worth noting that nine students who participated in the activities and who entered with non-STEM majors and six students who entered with health or environmental science majors switched to STEM majors and are currently enrolled.

Of the 138 students who participated in a one-time PDSA activity and not a semester-long or immersion program, 63 (45.7%) persisted in STEM while 75 (54.3%) left. Of those 75, 56 left the university and 19 switched to non-STEM majors. Sixteen of the students who persisted in STEM have graduated with Aerospace Engineering (2), Biochemistry (4), Biology (2), Biomedical Engineering (1), Chemical Engineering (3), Immunology and Medical Microbiology (1), and Forensic and Investigative Science (3) degrees. Two students who entered with non-STEM majors switched to STEM majors and are currently enrolled. One student who entered with a health science major switched to a STEM major and has graduated with a Chemistry degree.

Research Experiences

We tried to answer the question: “Are First2 students who participate in a research activity more likely to persist in STEM? We considered a research activity to be an activity where students engaged in research or presented about research. Out of the 125 students that participated in at least one First2 research activity, 60 (48.0%) remained in a STEM degree and 65 (52.0%) left.

Of the 125 students that started in a STEM degree

- 51 (40.8%) of them ended up dropping out of college
- 12 (9.6%) of the students switched their major to a non-STEM degree
- 3 (2.4%) of students switched to Psychology
- 1 (0.8%) of the students switched to a Health related major (1 to Exercise Physiology).
- 1 (0.8%) of the students switched to a STEM adjacent major (1 to Environmental Microbiology).

Students participating in a First2 research activity had a higher persistence rate in STEM (48.0%) than the current WVU STEM persistence rate (27%).

First Generation Students

We tried to answer the question: “Are first-gen students who are involved with First2 activities more likely to persist in STEM?” In our data set, there were 99 first-generation students. Out of the 99 first-generation students pursuing a STEM degree at WVU that participated in a First2 activity, 47 (47.5%) remained in a STEM degree and 52 (52.5%) left.

Of the 99 first-generation students that started in a STEM degree,

- 34 (34.3%) ended up dropping out
- 12 (12.1%) switched their major to a non-STEM degree
- 2 (2.0%) switched to Psychology
- 3 (3.0%) switched to a Health related major (1 to Exercise Physiology, 1 to a Healthcare Pathway, and 1 to Pre-Nursing)
- 3 (3.0%) switched to a STEM adjacent major (2 to Animal & Nutritional Sciences and 1 to Wildlife & Fisheries Resources).

First-generation students that participated in First2 activities had a higher persistence rate in STEM (47.5%) than the current WVU First-generation STEM persistence rate (18.6%).

APPENDIX

STEM Majors

- Aerospace Engineering
- Applied & Environmental Microbiology
- Biochemistry
- Biology
- Civil Engineering
- Computer Science
- Forensic Examiner
- Geology
- Mechanical Engineering
- Neuroscience
- STEM Pathway
- Aerospace Engineering
- Chemistry
- Biomedical Engineering
- Biomedical Sciences (UD)
- Biometric Systems Engineering
- Chemical Engineering
- Computer Engineering

- Data Science
- Forensic & Investigative Scien
- Forensic Science
- Game Dsgn and Interact Media
- GIS and Spatial Analysis
- Immunology & Medical Mcrblgy
- Industrial Engineering
- Pre-Physical Sciences
- Pre-Immunlgy & Medical Mcrblgy
- WVUIT-Biology
- WVUIT-Forensic Investigation
- WVUIT-Mechanical Engineering
- WVUIT-Civil Engineering
- Genetics & Developmntl Biology
- Mathematics
- Mining Engineering
- Petroleum & Natural Gas Engr
- Electrical Engineering
- Engineering Track 3
- Forensic Biology
- Forensic and Fraud Examination
- Pre-Engineering
- Forensic Chemistry
- Aerospace Engineering
- Engineering Track 1
- Forensic & Investigative Sci
- Engineering
- Environmental Geoscience
- Neuroscience
- Environmental Microbiology
- Physics
- Forensic and Fraud Examination
- Engineering Track 2

Health Related Majors

- Exercise Physiology
- Health and Well-Being
- Health Informatics/Info Mgt
- Healthcare Pathway

- Mental Health and Addiction St
- Public Health
- Public History
- Sport and Exercise Psychology
- Occupational Therapy
- Human Nutrition & Foods
- Medicine
- Audiology
- Pre-Health Professions
- Pre-Pharmacy
- Pharmacy - UG Direct Admit
- Pre-Dental Hygiene
- Dental Hygiene
- Dentistry
- Health Sciences
- Human Performance & Health
- Pharmacy - Professional
- Pre-Medical Laboratory Science
- Nursing
- Physical Therapy Professional
- Physician Assistant
- Public Health

Agricultural (STEM adjacent)

- Animal & Nutritional Sciences
- Energy Land Management
- Env & Energy Resources Mgmnt
- Environmental Geoscience
- Sustainable Food and Farming
- Wildlife & Fisheries Resources
- Environ, Soil & Water Science
- Wood Science and Technology
- Agricultural & Extension Ed
- Agroecology
- Agribusiness Management

Non-STEM

- Accountancy
- Accounting
- General Business
- Marketing

- Acting
- English
- Advertising & Public Relations
- Business and Comm Pathways
- Criminology
- Elementary Education
- Fashion, Dress, and Mrchdsng
- Interior Design
- Journalism
- Political Science
- Pre-Education
- Pre-Elementary Education
- Strategic Communications
- AMP ESL
- Undecided
- Anthropology
- Art Education
- Art History
- Women's and Gender Studies
- Graphic Design
- Art Therapy
- Athletic Coaching Education
- Pre-Athletic Training
- Athletic Training
- Physical Ed - Teacher Ed
- Business
- Communication Studies
- Exploratory Pathway
- Multidisciplinary Studies/BMdS
- Music Education
- Pre-Business
- Theatre Design & Technology
- Psychology
- Sport Management
- Business Administration
- Pre-Sociology
- Business Cybersecurity Mgmt
- Business Data Analytics
- Child Dev & Family Studies
- Coaching & Performance Science
- Comm Sciences and Disorders

- Music Industry
- Pre-Communication Studies
- Regents Bachelor of Arts
- Counseling
- Social Sciences Pathway
- Sociology
- Musical Theatre
- Dance
- Fashion, Dress, and Merchandising
- Design Studies
- Economics
- Multidisciplinary Studies
- Management
- English/Secondary Education
- Infant/Toddler Education
- Theatre

- French
- Entrepreneurship & Innovation
- International Studies
- Finance
- Management Information Systems
- UG Studies: EL HS Special
- Spanish
- General Arts and Sciences
- Geography
- Global Initiative
- Global Supply Chain Management
- High School Special
- Higher Education Administration
- History
- German Studies
- Pre Secondary Ed/Social Studies
- Religious Studies
- Integrated Marketing Communication
- Integrated Studies
- Social Studies/Secondary Education
- Visual and Performing Arts Pathway
- Interactive Design for Media
- Intermedia/Photography

- Landscape Architecture
- Law
- Leadership
- Liberal Arts and Hum Pathway
- Life-Span Development
- MDS - Education/Human Services
- General Studies (Engineering)
- Multidisciplinary Media Stud
- Pre-Media
- Social Work
- Music
- Music Perform: Instrumental
- Music Composition
- Music Therapy
- Music Perform: Piano
- Musicology
- Non-Degree
- Organizational Leadership
- Painting
- Performance
- Philosophy
- Pre-Criminology
- UG Studies (Undecided)
- Public Administration
- Rck Parks & Tourism Resources
- Secondary Education
- Pre-Criminology
- Pre-Sport Management
- WVUIT-Psychology
- Sports and Adventure Media
- Pre-Political Science
- Pre-Forensic & Invstgtv Sci
- Pre-Biology
- Sculpture
- Early Childhood Development
- Cultural Resource Management